

THE MOVEMENT OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN PROTECTING WOMEN'S RIGHTS AND THE CONTENT OF REFORMS IN OUR COUNTRY

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Aynisa Musurmanova

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor. Deputy director of the Research Institute "Family and Women" under the State Committee for Family

Akhmadalievna Khosiyatposhsho Abdukhayotovna

PhD Independent researcher of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Senior teacher at Uzbekistan State World Languages University Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract: The article describes the analysis of international experiences and statistical data in protecting the rights of women and girls, ensuring their political and economic literacy, high participation in society. Also, the actions taken to reform the social and political lifestyle of women in New Uzbekistan are highlighted.

Keywords: Foreign experience, New Uzbekistan, East Asia, women's rights, gender equality, politics, society, economy

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Abstract: В статье представлен анализ международного опыта и статистических данных по защите прав женщин и девочек, обеспечению их политической и экономической грамотности, высокой активности в жизни общества. Также освещаются действия, предпринятые по реформированию общественно-политического образа жизни женщин в Новом Узбекистане

Keywords: Зарубежный опыт, Новый Узбекистан, Восточная Азия, права женщин, гендерное равенство, политика, общество, экономика

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Abstract: Maqolada xotin qizlar huquqlarini himoya qilishda, ularning siyosiy va iqtisodiy savodxonligi, jamiyatda yuqori ishtirokini ta'minlash borasida xalqaro tajribalar va statistik ma'lumotlar tahlili bayoni etilgan. Shuningdek, Yangi O'zbekistonda ayollar ijtimoiy va siyosiy turmush tarzini isloh qilishda amalga oshirilayotgan harakatlar yoritilgan.

Keywords: Xorijiy tajriba, Yangi O'zbekiston, Sharqiy Osiyo, xotin qizlar huquqi, gender tenglik, siyosat, jamiyat, iqtisod.

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"Women hold up half of the sky" is an internationally popular Chinese proverb to affirm women's equal contribution and struggle for equal rights in health, education, economic opportunities and political participation.

Although rising prosperity in East Asia has narrowed gender gaps in these areas, women's political participation has not increased with the pace of economic development in the subregion. East Asia includes countries with a strong economy and a high human development rating not only in the Asia-Pacific region, but also in the world.

As seen in many societies in East Asia, rapid economic development has increased women's education, health and well-being, and reduced fertility rates

and reproductive obligations. These material improvements gave women more time to pursue economic and political goals outside the home. Still, societies can experience significant growth and development without equal gains for women's economic or political improvement. With over 1.3 billion people, the People's Republic of China (PRC) is the world's most populous country with the world's second largest economy. Japan has the second largest economy in the world, but has a much higher per capita income. However, in Japan, women are less represented in politics than in China, and social and gender practices in this country hinder women's political participation in East Asia. The predominance of women's domestic and reproductive roles as wives and mothers over other community-oriented and public roles is a characteristic of women all over the world, especially in East Asia. Gender attributes associated with these family roles, such as softness and passivity, are incompatible with social and active economic and political life, and women are considered incapable of fulfilling such roles. For example, the underrepresentation of women in China is explained by a "feudal" attitude that sees women as inferior and incapable of leadership. The official national women's organization, the All China Women's Federation (ACWF), has implemented programs to address these gender stereotypes. They advocated a two-pronged strategy: The first, targeting gender relations and the "feudal mindset" of men and women, and promoting a discourse of equality: the second, significantly improving women's political skills through educational programs, but political institutions structural barriers remain. Women's formal political participation and improvement is based on education and economic opportunities. Mongolia is one of the few places in the world where the education level of women is higher than that of men. Nevertheless, women's participation in the labor market lags behind men's, which means that the advantage in education has not yet lead to better results in women's employment. This is not much different in Japan, where secondary education is also high, but not reflected in economic or political participation. In the DPRK, women also have equal access to primary and secondary education, but this does not extend to university, where one in seven men completes one in 12 women. These examples show that education and economic participation alone are not enough to ensure women's political improvement - in socialist or democratic countries and at high or low levels of economic development.

Southeast Asian (SEA) societies claim a high status for women, but the relative gender imbalance and low level of political representation of women compared to the rest of the world is evident. This opposition can be explained by the persistence of patriarchal attitudes and gender stereotypes that generally discourage women from participating in politics. There is much heterogeneity within the Southeast

Asian region, and understanding how gender relations operate in each distinct cultural, social, and economic context is essential to explaining this heterogeneity. Traditional attitudes that limit women's political participation include unequal human development and women's limited access to food, land, property, finance, technology, education, training and economic opportunities in developing countries where these resources are themselves scarce is strengthened. Marriage, divorce, and inheritance customs, as well as rates of gender-based violence and sexual and reproductive health, affect not only the well-being of women, especially poor or marginalized women, but also their ability to engage in political activity are decisive factors. Of particular concern is how societies and governments respond to these personal status or family-related injustices, as well as, women themselves advocating for changes in norms and laws to address these injustices.

Human development is a necessary, if not sufficient, condition for guaranteeing women's representation or gender equality. Increasing the political activity of women in SEA requires the formation of an equal political culture that encourages and values women's participation in the medium term. Another important factor limiting women's political participation is the lack of material resources available to women. Politics in South Asia is about money, power and political networks. It is almost impossible to participate in any election without using sufficient financial and political knowledge and preparation. As women are less integrated into strong political and economic networks, it is more difficult for them to participate in large numbers or play a significant role in political decision-making.

South Asian women are economically disadvantaged and gender biases prevent them from developing political connections early in their education and careers to prepare them for future political roles. Some parties have separate women's wings, but instead of empowering women or expressing their solidarity, they often marginalize women further.

Education is often cited as a prerequisite for women's political participation. In rural areas, women with little or minimal education have achieved a high level of political activity. While this may help make women aware of opportunities and the existence of gender imbalances in society, despite the popular belief that education is critical to women's political empowerment, many women in South Asia remain politically inactive without formal education and training went to the field. Rural women, despite their lack of education, are often very politically aware. Bihar Chief Minister Rabi Devi is a prime example of this. Although she was widely criticized as an illiterate village woman who succeeded her husband, who was arrested for fraud, in one of India's least developed states, she stood her ground and played her political role comfortably for many years and accepted with confidence. With

education comes greater access to economic opportunity, but lack of formal education in South Asia does not necessarily affect political aspirations and outcomes. This is evidenced by the significant increase in political participation of rural women at the Zila parishad and Panchayat (district and village) levels due to gender quotas (discussed below).

Today, it is possible to observe that the level of political and legal culture and social activity of women is increasing in all levels of state and social administration of our country, in the judicial system, in the activities of non-governmental organizations, in social systems, in general, in all spheres of the life of our society. Currently, 17% of the members of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 16% of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber are women, and hundreds of women people's deputies are actively working in regional, city and district councils. 35% of entrepreneurs working in Uzbekistan, 10% of farmers are women.

The experience and achievements of our country in the comprehensive protection of women's rights and interests, as well as their active participation in the life of the state and society, are of great interest worldwide. In particular, this topic is considered and discussed at the highest levels, within multilateral institutions such as the United Nations, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, the Commonwealth of Independent States, and other organizations. The Republic of Uzbekistan always pays special attention to ensuring women's rights. Uzbekistan was one of the first in Central Asia to join the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women on May 6, 1995. It has also ratified the Convention on Protection of Motherhood, the Convention on Discrimination in the Field of Labor and Profession, and other international documents.

Since Uzbekistan joined the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, six periodic reports have been submitted to the UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women.

Thanks to consistent legislation and other measures aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms and interests of women, they are successfully exercising their rights and freedoms, knowledge and skills in entrepreneurship, education, health, science and socio-political fields.

In 2022, the State Committee for Family and Women of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional divisions were established, and one of its priorities is to provide comprehensive support to women and ensure gender equality.

In order to support women in every way, Support state fund was established to activate participation in the organization of family and private entrepreneurship,

handicrafts, helping them acquire knowledge and skills in the professions required in today's labor market.

The Republican Commission for the Systematic Solution of Women's Problems and Social Support was established, and its main task is to organize work on the study of women's problems in the regions, systematic solution, reduction of poverty and increase of the population's well-being.

In the field of ensuring the rights of women in the field of labor and employment:

In accordance with the amendments to the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, bans on engaging women in certain fields or professions were canceled, as well as. a new recommended list of fields or professions that have a negative impact on women's health was approved.

It is prohibited to cancel an employment contract concluded for an indefinite period, as well as, a fixed-term employment contract before the end of its term, due to the fact that women have reached the retirement age before the age of 60 or have created the right to receive an old-age pension according to the law.

"Women's Entrepreneurship Centers" were established in the form of a business incubator at the expense of the Public Fund for the Support of Women and Families consists of preparation. For women who have successfully mastered a special educational program, preferential loans with a minimum 3-year, 6-month grace period and an annual interest rate of 8 percent will be granted for the organization of business activities at the expense of the Fund and international organizations.

"Social, economic and legal protection of women, creation of suitable conditions for improving their well-being in every way is one of the priorities of the state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Trade unions of the country are actively participating in this process. In particular, the Council of the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan is carrying out systematic work to ensure women's socio-economic interests and labor rights. At the same time, the experience of our country in the field of social support for women is being studied by the world community.

In the law on measures to further strengthen guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship the following points are covered

- to attract women who have expressed a desire to engage in entrepreneurship to the centers and assist in the organization of entrepreneurial activities;
- formation of women's skills in organizing and running their own business, consulting assistance in the preparation of business ideas, including preparation of a project business plan, selection and application of different taxation regimes, accounting, modern information technologies organization of training in use and other directions;

- in necessary cases, to help women entrepreneurs who are starting their activity to allocate space from vacant buildings in neighborhoods;
- providing necessary advice and practical assistance to women entrepreneurs and women who express their desire to engage in entrepreneurship in setting up their own business, including finding reliable partners, assisting in the purchase of mini-technologies and equipment, sales of manufactured products help to be done.

Today, in our country, the issue of supporting women, ensuring their rights and legal interests is identified as one of the main and priority directions of state policy, and we are also witnessing the results of the reforms and efforts being implemented in this regard.

The news provided in the comprehensive plan of measures aimed at the implementation of the National Program for 2022-2026 on increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life in 2022-2023 fully confirms our opinion. In particular, the action plan, which consists of 6 main directions and 112 points, aims to increase the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life and the news that will be the basis has been reflected.

As a result of the reforms carried out in recent years, the number of women in our national parliament has reached the level of 32% according to the recommendations set by the UN. The share of women in the field of entrepreneurship is 35 percent and in higher education is higher than 46 percent. About 1,500 professional women are working in various levels of leadership positions in the state administration, the share of women in the system is 33 percent, and this figure is growing rapidly.

A completely new direction in the social protection system - "Women's Register", "Youth Register" and "Iron Register" was introduced to study and solve women's problems. On the basis of the "Women's Register" over the past 3 years, about 400,000 women have been employed. Systematic measures are being implemented to provide housing, improve living and working conditions, and increase income of the needy.

Our state pays special attention to women's health. Because the health of the society is characterized, first of all, by how healthy women are. As the President noted, "...attention to mother and child health is attention to society and the future".

In short, the state appears as the main reformer in the protection of women's dignity, rights and freedoms in society. Indeed, the issue of expressing the rights and interests of women in society, further increasing the place and role of women in state and society relations, and protecting their interests in the political, legal,

and social spheres is one of the main conditions for the formation of the Third Renaissance generation in New Uzbekistan.

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